

Assessment of Supply Chain Designs Considering Uncertainty via a Monte Carlo Simulation

Bewertung für die Gestaltung von Supply-Chains unter Berücksichtigung von Unsicherheiten mittels Monte-Carlo-Simulation

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Abstract: In today's volatile and uncertain environment, designing resilient and cost-effective supply chains is increasingly complex. This paper presents a Monte Carlo simulation-based approach for supplier selection and order allocation (SSOA) under uncertainty. We propose a dual-criteria decision-making model that evaluates both procurement-related costs and service level, measured by days without stock. The model incorporates probabilistic inputs for demand fluctuations, delivery delays, and supplier stockout risks. For the development of our modelling approach, we define seven sourcing scenarios for which we simulate a 12-month period using real-world inspired data. Risk measures such as Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Conditional VaR (CVaR) are used to assess worst-case outcomes. The study highlights the value of simulation in capturing complex uncertainties and supporting strategic sourcing decisions.

1 Introduction

Globalization and market liberalization have driven companies to establish globally dispersed supply chains, impacting sales markets, company sites, and sourcing strategies. Designing such value chains involves many tasks, including customer demand forecast, design of distribution structures, selection and parameterization of inventory policies as well as the choice of transport modes and frequencies. For production, firms must determine capacity, manufacturing strategies, and make-or-buy decisions. On the procurement side, selecting suppliers, setting ordering policies, and allocating volumes across multiple sources are key considerations.

These design choices significantly affect cost and performance. Many quantitative models from economics, logistics, and operations research support supply chain planning and require knowledge about the exact value of input variables. In practice, uncertainties such as demand fluctuations or varying supplier performance exist. These uncertainties can be modelled using probability distributions. Traditional

inventory policies cover these uncertainties (e.g., demand fluctuation) on a local scale. However, capturing disruptions across the entire supply chain, and research on uncertainty issues remains a common focus in academia (Riad et al., 2024).

To address this, we propose a Monte Carlo simulation-based approach for supply chain design, initially applied to supplier selection and order allocation (SSOA). Chapter 2 reviews the literature, Chapter 3 introduces our model, and Chapter 4 presents experimental results. The paper concludes with managerial insights and an outlook on future model development and practical applications in Chapter 5.

2 State-of-the-Art Literature on Monte Carlo Simulation in Supply Chain Design and Decision-Making

Monte Carlo (MC) simulation has emerged as a powerful tool for evaluating uncertainty in supply chain design, supplier selection, and risk management. One major focus is MC simulation for performance evaluation of supply chains. Deleris and Erhun (2004) present an early yet influential framework using MC simulation for risk management in supply networks, emphasizing quantification of rare but high-impact events. Ozkan and Kilic (2011) present a methodology for estimating reliability in logistics networks, integrating MC simulation to account for component failure rates and network disruption scenarios. Dotoli et al. (2014) combine Data Envelopment Analysis and MC simulation to rank suppliers under stochastic input conditions. Schmitt and Singh (2022) employ both MC and discrete-event simulation to quantify disruption risk, demonstrating the importance of simulation in capturing variability that is difficult to model analytically.

Another significant stream of literature integrates MC simulation with optimization approaches to support decision-making under uncertainty. Mangla et al. (2014) focus on risk management in green supply chains using MC to simulate operational uncertainties and evaluate environmental impacts. Moghaddam (2015) applies goal programming in closed-loop networks, offering a practical method to balance profitability with environmental and risk considerations on supplier selection using MC simulation to solve the problem. Kabiri et al. (2022) develop a simulation-optimization framework for multi-objective production-distribution planning, leveraging non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm and MC simulation to capture conflicting goals and uncertain parameters. Bhowmik and Pavez (2024) combine mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) with MC simulation to design supply chain robustness against stochastic demand.

Despite notable progress, several gaps persist. First, MC simulation integration is rare in supplier selection under disruption risks. Models in Lin et al. (2025) or Sajid et al. (2025) address uncertainty linguistically but lack simulation-based stress testing of outcomes. Second, several optimisation-based studies assume known and fixed parameters, overlooking probabilistic inputs, which reduces realism in volatile settings. Finally, while more studies focus on Monte Carlo simulation-based analysis in supply chain management, fewer address its application in structuring supply chain design – though notable exceptions include Moghaddam (2015) and Kabiri et al. (2022).

3 Model Formulation

3.1 Modelling Assumptions

Based on the literature review and research gaps, we will develop a dual-criteria decision making framework for SSOA and SC designs assessment without giving weights for these two criteria: (1) total procurement-related cost; (2) service level (in this article we use days without stock). The manufacturer category in this research follows a Make-to-Stock (MTS) strategy due to that MTS allows SC costs to accumulate over time (Belvárdi et al. 2012). The product produced by the manufacturer is not specified as we aim for our model to be applied to different SCs. Our focus is on the core part (CP) of the final product, and we assume that each unit of the final product requires one CP for assembly. In accordance with the ISO 14051 guidelines for material flow cost accounting (MFCA) (ISO, 2011), material costs, system costs, and waste management costs are determined. Based on ISO 14051 and the purpose of the model, the cost elements considered are as follows:

1. Purchasing cost. Transportation cost for raw materials is in practice generally included in the unit price, thus we exclude transportation cost for this model.
2. Inventory cost. As presented by (Heizer et al. 2017), inventory cost equals to the sum of holding cost, ordering cost, and setup cost. We assume that ordering and setup cost are covered by the administrative, shipping and other logistics costs in the unit price and production setup cost are not independent from procurement.

3.2 Dual-Criteria SSOA Decision Making Framework via MC Simulation

The SSOA decision making framework consists of four stages. Different SC design scenarios based on different order allocation shares are defined first, followed by data gathering. The third stage focuses on the modelling and simulation running processes and the fourth stage analyses the results.

Based on the number of suppliers for the CP, there are various SC design scenarios: single sourcing, dual sourcing, and multi-sourcing schemes. The main difference among these scenarios is the order allocation shares.

In the remainder of the article, we will use the following parameters and variables.

Indices

S : Set of suppliers i ; T : Set of periods j ; k_i : Order allocation percentage from each supplier; ed_j : integer, estimated demand for the final product in each period; rd_j : integer, real demand for the final product in each period; fr_j : fluctuation rate of demand in each period; dl_{ij} : integer, delay in delivery for CP from each supplier in each period (days); so_{ij} : stockout rate from each supplier in each period; $P_i(dl_{ij})$: probability density function (PDF) of delay in delivery from each supplier in each period; $P_i(so_{ij})$: PDF of stockout rates from each supplier in each period; pcp_i : unit price of the CP from each supplier; mcp : market price of each CP; mcp : market price of each CP; s : average monthly storage cost per unit; or : obsolescence rate for the CP; ir : insurance rate for the CP; c : cost of capital for the inventory.

Intermediary variables

a_{ij} : integer, available units of the CP from each supplier in each period; ta_j : integer,

total available CPs in each period; ls_j : left stock in each period that will be carried over to the next period; dws_j : days without stock in each period.

Result variables

TPC_j : total purchasing cost in each period; SC_j : storage cost for the CP in each period; CC_j : capital cost for the CP in each period; IC_j : insurance cost for the CP in each period; OC_j : obsolescence cost for the CP in each period; TC : total costs over all the periods; DWS : days without stock per year.

The equations that we are going to use for the modelling process are as follows:

$$rd_j \sim \text{Uniform}[ed_j(1 - fr_j), ed_j(1 + fr_j)], \forall j \in T \quad (1)$$

$$a_{ij} = (1 - sr_{ij}) \left(1 - \frac{dl_{ij}}{30}\right) k_i \times rd_j, \forall i \in S, \forall j \in T \quad (2)$$

$$ta_j = \sum_i \max(0, a_{ij}) + ls_{j-1}, \forall j \in T \quad (3)$$

$$ls_j = \max(0, ta_j - rd_j), \forall j \in T, ls_0 = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$dws_j = \max\left[0, \min\left(dl_{1j} - \frac{ls_{j-1} * 30}{rd_j}, \dots, dl_{ij} - \frac{ls_{j-1} * 30}{rd_j}, \dots\right)\right], \forall j \in T \quad (5)$$

$$SC_j = s \times ta_j \times \frac{1}{2}, \forall j \in T \quad (6)$$

$$CC_j = c \times ta_j \times \frac{1}{2}, \forall j \in T \quad (7)$$

$$OC_j = or \times ta_j \times \frac{1}{2}, \forall j \in T \quad (8)$$

$$IC_j = ir \times ta_j \times \frac{1}{2}, \forall j \in T \quad (9)$$

$$TPC_j = \sum_i (pcp_i \times a_{ij}), \forall j \in T \quad (10)$$

$$TC = \sum_j (TPC_j + SC_j + CC_j + OC_j + IC_j) \quad (11)$$

$$DWS = \sum_j dws_j \quad (12)$$

Equation (1) describes the real demand for CPs in each period, which follows a uniform distribution fluctuating within a defined range. Equation (2) computes the number of available CPs supplied by each supplier in each period. Equation (3) calculates the total quantity of CPs that can be stored and consumed during each period. Equation (4) calculates the leftover stock of CPs in each period and ensures that no inventory remains from the previous period at the start of the first period. Equation (5) calculates the number of days without stock in each period. Equation (6) describes the storage cost for CPs in each period, while Equations (7), (8), and (9) calculate the capital cost, obsolescence cost, and insurance cost, respectively. Equation (10) computes total purchasing cost for CPs in each period, Equation (11) presents the total procurement relevant cost for CPs, and Equation (12) calculates the total number of days without stock over all the periods.

This model has been implemented in Python. The execution steps are as follows.

- STEP 1: Initialize parameters.
- STEP 2: Define the probability distributions for delivery and stockout risks.
- STEP 3: Run the simulations for multiple periods. For each iteration, repeat the following steps for each period.
- STEP 4: Simulate over periods (12 months): real demand, delivery delays, stockout rates, available CPs, and demand fulfilment.
- STEP 5: Calculate the cost components and aggregate them for all the periods.
- STEP 6: Repeat for all scenarios.
- STEP 7: Simulation results visualisation.

4 Numerical Experiment and Analysis

The dual-criteria Monte Carlo simulation-based decision-making framework for SSOA is validated through a numerical experiment, where it is assumed that three suppliers provide the CPs. We use totally seven order allocation scenarios (see Tab. 1) to show different allocation shares, and all the relevant analysis is based on the seven scenarios. Scenarios 1 – 3 presents single sourcing, Scenarios 4 – 7 are multi-sourcing ones.

Table 1: 7 allocation shares from the seven scenarios

Scenario	k_1	k_2	k_3
1	100 %	0 %	0 %
2	0 %	100 %	0 %
3	0 %	0 %	100 %
4	50 %	50 %	0 %
5	50 %	0 %	50 %
6	0 %	50 %	50 %
7	33.33 %	33.33 %	33.33 %

As follows in Table 2 are the input parameters of the simulation. The simulation uses key input parameters including expected demand 1000 units per period and fluctuation rate 10%. Delivery delays and stockout risks for each supplier follow discrete probability distributions.

The MC simulation is conducted across 5000 iterations to evaluate the impact of delivery and stockout risks on the total supply chain costs for the CP, and at the same time the impact of different SC scenarios on total procurement-related cost and days without stock is calculated. The simulation covers a period of 12 months, with the cost components including storage, purchasing, capital, obsolescence, and insurance. The primary KPIs identified in this model include average total cost across all periods over all runs, average cost per component, average days without stock per year and risk-related metrics (VaR and CVaR).

Table 2: Input of the Monte Carlo simulation

Input	Value
ed_j	1000
fr_j	10 %
dl_{ij}	$dl_{1j} = \begin{cases} 0, P_1 = 0.60 \\ 2, P_1 = 0.20 \\ 5, P_1 = 0.10 \\ 9, P_1 = 0.08 \\ 15, P_1 = 0.02 \end{cases}, dl_{2j} = \begin{cases} 0, P_2 = 0.40 \\ 2, P_2 = 0.20 \\ 4, P_2 = 0.10 \\ 6, P_2 = 0.20 \\ 8, P_2 = 0.10 \end{cases}, dl_{3j} = \begin{cases} 0, P_3 = 0.50 \\ 5, P_3 = 0.30 \\ 10, P_3 = 0.10 \\ 12, P_3 = 0.05 \\ 15, P_3 = 0.05 \end{cases}$
sr_{ij}	$sr_{1j} = \begin{cases} 0, P_1 = 0.50 \\ 0.05, P_1 = 0.15 \\ 0.10, P_1 = 0.10 \\ 0.15, P_1 = 0.15 \\ 0.20, P_1 = 0.10 \end{cases}, sr_{2j} = \begin{cases} 0, P_2 = 0.80 \\ 0.05, P_2 = 0.10 \\ 0.10, P_2 = 0.07 \\ 0.15, P_2 = 0.02 \\ 0.20, P_2 = 0.01 \end{cases}, sr_{3j} = \begin{cases} 0, P_3 = 0.35 \\ 0.05, P_3 = 0.15 \\ 0.10, P_3 = 0.20 \\ 0.15, P_3 = 0.20 \\ 0.20, P_3 = 0.10 \end{cases}$
pcp_i	$pcp_1 = 27, pcp_2 = 30, pcp_3 = 25$
mcp	35
or	0.02
ir	0.006
s	2
c	0.05

Table 3 presents the average total cost and days without stock per year over all the simulation runs in each scenario.

Table 3: Average, VaR, CVaR values of total cost and days without stock per year

	Total procurement-related cost			Days without stock per year		
	Average	VaR	CVaR	Average	VaR	CVaR
Scenario 1	309302	330668	335381	23.12	44.00	49.99
Scenario 2	345476	366234	370625	33.53	50.00	53.84
Scenario 3	263721	288277	294287	46.09	74.00	80.32
Scenario 4	327201	343490	347666	9.09	19.00	22.06
Scenario 5	286264	303364	307874	9.42	21.00	24.43
Scenario 6	304534	321979	325987	14.95	28.00	31.65
Scenario 7	302730	316951	320475	4.25	12.00	14.00

From the perspective of average total cost, Scenario 3 is the best solution to supplier selection which means that the manufacturer only orders CPs from Supplier 3. The largest difference is 81755 euros per year. From the perspective of average days without stock, Scenario 7 performs better than other scenarios with the largest difference being 41.84 days.

Using the simulation results, we break down the cost components as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Mean of each cost component over all simulations for each scenario

The total purchasing cost accounts for almost 90% of the total cost in the experiment. Other cost components account for less percentages, among which capital cost and storage cost contribute the most. Scenario 3 is the best order allocation mix, given that Supplier 3 offers the cheapest CP. Among Scenarios 4 – 6, Scenario 5 performs the best, indicating that no orders from Supplier 2 causes the total cost to reduce, easily understandable from the given unit prices in Table 2.

VaR and CVaR are significant indicators for risk assessment when managers want to focus on the tail end of the distribution. We plot the total cost distribution and days without stock with VaR and CVaR at a 95% confidence level, illustrated in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2 provides a view of the total cost distribution over 5000 simulations for the seven scenarios. It is easy to conclude as Figure 1 does that Scenario 3 is the best in terms of total cost since there are the smallest values of VaR and CVaR in Scenario 3. Scenario 7 has the narrowest distributions while Scenarios 1 – 3 have wider ones, suggesting more predictable and stable cost performance for Scenario 7, which demonstrates the advantage of supplier diversification in controlling supply chain risk and associated costs.

Figure 2: Total cost distribution with VaR and CVaR (95 %) for seven scenarios

Figure 3: Days without stock distribution with VaR and CVaR (95 %) for seven scenarios

A similar conclusion can be drawn from the Ridgeline plot of days without stock per year in Figure 3. Scenario 7 exhibits the narrowest distribution, indicating high stability, while Scenarios 1 to 3 display much wider distributions, reflecting greater variability. In terms of stock availability, Scenario 7 results in the fewest days without stock per year, demonstrating its superior performance in maintaining inventory continuity.

Figure 4 compares the seven scenarios based on the two criteria at the same time. Among Scenarios 1, 2, 5, and 6, Scenario 5 emerges as the most favorable option, offering both the lowest average total cost and the fewest average days without stock per year. Scenario 7 also outperforms Scenario 4, and the comparison between Scenario 5 and Scenario 4 clearly favors Scenario 5, as the difference in stockout days is minor (only 0.51 days). Likewise, Scenario 5 is clearly preferable to Scenario 3. The final comparison lies between Scenarios 5 and 7. If decision-makers prioritize service level, Scenario 5 stands out as the optimal choice.

Figure 4: Comparison of the seven scenarios: total cost versus days without stock

Instead of relying solely on average value markers, we can use dot clusters to compare the full distribution of outcomes across scenarios. For example, the comparison between Scenario 2 and Scenario 7 is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 clearly shows that Scenario 7 outperforms Scenario 2 on both dimensions: it consistently results in lower total costs and fewer days without stock. The cluster of Scenario 7 is concentrated in the lower-left region of the plot, indicating both cost

efficiency and high supply availability. In contrast, Scenario 2 exhibits significantly higher total costs and greater variability in stockout days, with points spread widely across a larger range. This visual evidence supports the superiority of Scenario 7 in balancing cost control and resilience.

Figure 5: Comparison of Scenario 2 and 7: total cost versus days without stock

5 Conclusions and Outlook

Today's VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity) world is very challenging for the design of resilient supply chains. Our research presented here indicates, that Monte Carlo simulation-based models can be beneficial for these design tasks by providing a systematic approach to model uncertainty and variability for supply chain operations. One of the primary benefits of this approach is to model complex systems with a moderate set of variables to simulate a wide range of scenarios. Through this, businesses can identify potential risks and opportunities, leading to more informed decision-making based on the quantification of uncertainty. Enterprises can assess the supply chain costs and performances not only for an expected average case but can determine these figures for difference VaR settings.

The approach presented here is only the beginning of a method to design supply chains using Monte Carlo simulation. In our work so far, we have limited our modeling focus to the material supply. The number of parts and suppliers considered is very small. For further work, we therefore aim to increase the complexity of the upstream supply chain (more suppliers, different modes of transports, different parts). In addition, we aim to consider the modelling of production and distribution.

Finally, the approach presented here needs to be tested in real-world supply chains to obtain feedback on the modelling effort and the traceability of the results. Even though we are still in an early phase of development of our approach, we are confident that Monte Carlo simulation is an important tool for designing supply chains in the VUCA world.

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